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**Technical note on influence of calibration gaps and dead
sub-samples**

Technical Note TN-3

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1 Influence of calibration gaps

The CAIRT instrument regularly performs calibration measurements (e.g., black body, deep space). This leads to gaps in the atmospheric observations. The length of these gaps depends on the hardware and the calibration scenario. Due to the limb observation geometry, the information of the measured spectra extends far beyond the actual tangent point. Short gaps hence may be closed by the tomographic retrievals. In contrast, for larger gaps also a substantial loss of observations at the edges of the gaps are expected due to the no longer overlapping line of sights. The aim of this report is to investigate, for which gap length a) no significant information loss occurs, b) information loss is restricted to the region of the gap and c) information loss spreads beyond the gap.

Based on the results of Ungermann (2022), in this technical note we investigate the effect of measurement gaps on the observation performance of gravity waves (GWs). We compare a reference data set without any data gaps to a case with a given number of consecutive missing observations along the orbit. Since GW estimation is sensitive to noise and observation quality, it is a prime candidate to estimate how measurement gaps affect the instrument's performance to meet the set science objectives. In particular, we investigate the observed horizontal and vertical wavelengths, temperature amplitudes, and GW momentum flux (GWMF).

1.1 Setup & Experiment

The setup of the retrieval is identical to the one used in Ungermann (2022). For the gap length, we chose multiple realistic setups of 4, 6, 7, and 9 missing spectra every 30th measurement along the orbit. These gap lengths are realistic for the planned black body calibration measurements that are discussed. The gap lengths correspond to discarding between 13 – 30% of the measured spectra before the temperature, and subsequently, the GW spectra are retrieved. We have chosen this configuration (gaps repeating every 30 observations) in order to maximize the number of gaps per data set, but without causing overlaps of the influence of the gaps. In addition, the number and position of gaps is identical between the different setups. This differs from the requirement set in Ungermann (2022) (gaps separated by at least 50 contiguous spatial samples), where the data quality was in focus - here, however, we want to focus on the data influence in and around the gaps and thus we chose to increase the number of gaps.

Figure 1 shows an example distribution of gaps with length of 6 ALT samples along the orbit of one day of measurements. The test period is one week of high-resolution ECMWF data, from January 6 to January 13, 2006. This data has already been investigated for its GW content in Höpfner et al. (2023).

Figure 1 Approximate location of the gaps (red) in the observed spectra. Note that the location shows only roughly the tangent point location, which varies with altitude.

The GW analysis performed on the retrieved temperature is identical to the one used for Höpfner et al. (2023). The analysis cuboid sizes for the 6 wave components are recapitulated in Tab. 1. These 6 wave components correspond to 6 wave modes that are fitted in each cuboid, i.e., up to 6 superposed GWs are analyzed. A refit of the amplitude has been performed for each wave component in smaller-sized cubes. The refitting is required because the amplitude of GWs can vary strongly across the fitting cuboid. For a better estimate of the amplitude at the cuboid center, the size is reduced before each detected wave is refit.

Table 1 Sizes of the analysis cubes used for the GW retrieval (in retrieval grid points). The extent of the cuboids depends on the resolution, i.e., 50 km along-track, 25 km across-track, and 1 km in the vertical.

Wave component	Cuboid size [pt]		
	along track	across track	vertical
1 & 2	11	9	11
3 & 4	7	9	11
5 & 6	5	7	11
refit	5	7	5

1.2 Results

1.2.1 GW spectra

The influence of gaps in the retrieval on the GW spectra can be seen in Fig. 2. Panel a shows the reference spectrum, panel b–e the respective spectrum with measurement gaps of 4, 6, 7, and 9 points, or ALT samples, in length. The main features of the reference spectrum, i.e., a spectral

maximum around 8 km vertical and 750 km horizontal wavelength tapering of to every direction, are still visible. However, there are strongly increased short horizontal wavelengths shorter than about 100 km horizontal wavelength, which are spurious artifacts in the GW distributions. If these short-scale waves are not properly removed in post processing, they could deteriorate the GW product.

The general feature that can be seen in Fig. 2 is the widening of the spectra. While they are pretty much confined between about 100–1000 km horizontal wavelengths without gaps and small gaps of 4 ALT samples length, the spectrum extends to very short horizontal scales for gaps of length 6 ALT samples and beyond. The widening of the spectrum and shift to very short horizontal wavelengths can be seen more clearly in the horizontal cross sections shown in Fig. 3.

In a previous assessment of global GW spectra (Rhode et al. 2024), we stated that for a reduction of the influence of retrieval noise on the GW products, the spectra should be cropped at around 100 km horizontal wavelength (shown in the magenta box in Fig. 2a; see also Höpfner et al.; 2023). The valid region has been estimated to be between 100 km and 3500 km for the horizontal wavelength and between 2.8 km and 33 km for the vertical wavelength. Compared with the spectra in Fig. 2b–e, this filter will remove most of the contributions introduced by the measurement gaps.

Figure 2 Global wavelength spectrum of detected GWs for reference retrieval (a) and retrieval with gaps of lengths 4, 6, 7, and 9 ALT samples, respectively (b – e). The data is representative

for an altitude of 30 km and 6th of January 2006. The blue and red ci circles depict the main GW spectrum and the spurious spectrum due to noise, respectively.

Figure 3 Sub-spectra for vertical wavelengths between 2 and 4 km (top) and 8 and 10 km (bottom). The lines correspond to horizontal cross sections in Fig. 2. Note the logarithmic axes.

1.2.2 Effect on GWMF

The global distribution of absolute GWMF after applying the aforementioned filtering to the GW spectra is shown in Fig. 4 for the reference simulation and measurement gaps of length 6. Note that the distribution shows both data inside and outside of the gaps.¹ In general, both distributions are very comparable and show only slight differences in regions with lower GWMF, i.e., regions where the algorithm might detect introduced noise as GWs due to the lack of actual GW perturbations. This lies in the nature of the spectral analysis: it will pick up the strongest wave-like perturbation in the cuboids. If the noise perturbation becomes large in comparison to the atmospheric perturbations, the noise might be fitted instead. A similar agreement can be seen for the horizontal wavelengths and temperature amplitudes of the individually determined GWs (not shown).

¹ Note again that the retrieval takes advantage of the full information along the line of sight, thereby extending the temperature retrieval into the gap. The data in and adjacent to the gap will, however, be estimated from a lower number of line of sights and, therefore, less accurate.

Figure 4 Horizontal distribution of absolute GWMF for the retrieval without (a) and with (b) measurement gaps of length 6 ALT samples at 30 km altitude. (As Fig. 5 suggests, the wider gaps show even less blue than panel (b).)

A second comparison for the effect on GWMF is the zonal mean GWMF shown in Fig. 5. Plotted are the reference simulation and the four simulations with measurement gaps. The main features of the distribution are preserved even with 9 missing ALT samples. However, the minimum GWMF in regions where the reference shows almost no GWMF increases strongly with increasing gap length. In other words, an increasing gap length increases the noise floor in the observed GWMF and thus limits the ability of the instrument to see lower amplitude GW events. Considering Fig. 5, the gap length should be limited to 7 ALT samples or shorter as this is still a very reasonable noise level (comparable to 6 ALT samples but less restrictive).

Figure 5 Zonal mean absolute GWMF of the global distributions exemplified in Fig. 4 for all study setups. Note the logarithmic scale for better distinguishing of the different scenarios.

1.2.3 Phase-speed - direction spectra

The effect of the missing measurements on the phase speed spectra is shown in Fig. 6. Gaps of 4 and 6 measurements (Fig. 6b and c) have a limited effect on the slow phase speeds of high

GWMF (bright segments in the center of the plots) compared to the reference without any missing data (Fig. 6a). However, for faster GWs, the spectrum is not well represented anymore: the dominant direction for these fast GWs is still part of the spectrum but additional noise dilutes the visibility of it (non-directional background particularly visible around 20m/s phase-speed). Therefore, the direction is not well determined for this part of the spectrum.

Increasing the number of missing observations to 7 and 9 (Fig. 6d and e) leads to a strong deterioration of the derived phase speed spectrum. The slow phase speed part of the spectrum is still represented reasonably but the fast GWS are completely overshadowed by spurious signals. This renders the GWs faster than about 20 ms^{-1} completely uninformative and indiscernible from the background noise. These fast GWs, however, are the ones that more often propagate up to the mesosphere, where they drive the overarching meridional circulation. Keeping this part of the spectrum resolved is crucial for the science objective of assessing the atmospheric circulation.

Figure 6 Phase speed spectra as determined from the observations without gaps (a) and for gaps of 4, 6, 7, and 9 consecutive measurements (b, c, d, and e, respectively) at 30 km altitude. The color shading gives the summed GWMF in the respective bin. Note the logarithmic scale.

For another view on the quality of the spectra, Fig. 7 and 8 show the phase speed spectra for the data within the measurement gap and outside of the gaps, respectively. As can be seen, the phase speed spectra outside of the gaps are mostly preserved (Fig. 8) except for faster phase speeds. Deterioration of the phase speed spectra are mostly seen within the gap, as would be suspected. The slowest phase speeds are rather well preserved up to gaps of 7 ALT samples. However, there are increasingly strong artefacts in the east-west direction with increasing phase speeds with gap length. Once the gaps are 9 ALT samples wide, the central part starts to vanish and the noise covers almost all phase speeds.

Figure 7 Phase speed spectra of the S3D results obtained within the measurement gaps for gap lengths of 4, 6, 7, and 9 consecutive measurements (panel a, b, c, and d, respectively).

Figure 8 The same as Fig. 7 but for all S3D results outside of the measurement gaps.

1.2.4 Parameter comparison

For further analysis of differences introduced by the measurements on individual waves, Fig. 9 shows a comparison of determined GW characteristics between the reference and measurement gap data sets. In addition, the values have been separated by their spatial location compared to the measurement gaps. The right column of Fig. 9 shows all values that are directly co-located with a measurement gap (i.e., the samples within the measurement gaps), and the left column shows the complementary rest of the data points (i.e., the samples outside of the measurement gaps). The collocation with the gaps is done by checking whether the central point of the cuboid lies within the segment of missing ALT samples.

Figure 9a and b show the absolute GWMF determined from the GW observations. Both the reference and the data including gaps of 6 ALT samples agree fairly well if outside of the gaps, especially for higher GWMF. For small GWMF, there is a larger spread of the determined values, which can be attributed to the added fluctuations leading to spurious low-amplitude GWs as already seen in the previous section. The observations close to the measurement gaps on the other hand show a stronger deviation from perfect agreement: as was argued before, there is GWMF detected in the data where it can't be observed in the reference data. This is related to the measurement gaps leading to some fluctuations falsely picked up as low-amplitude GWs.

Similar arguments are valid for the horizontal wavelengths (Fig. 9c and d) and the temperature amplitudes (Fig. 9e and f). The horizontal wavelength seems to be rather unaffected by the measurement gaps, although some previously shorter wavelengths are now mapped to longer scales (Fig. 9c, points to the left of the gray identity line). The temperature amplitude is robust concerning measurement gaps for high-amplitude GWs.

Figure 9 Comparison of determined GW parameters in the reference data set (horizontal axes) and the data with measurement gaps of 6 ALT samples (vertical axes) separated by location: left column shows only values at the rough locations where measurements were taken; right column at roughly the locations of the measurement gaps. The two rows show absolute GWMF and horizontal wavelength, respectively. The color shading gives the sum of absolute GWMF in the respective bin, where the right column is scaled to the number of points in the left column.

Note the logarithmic color scale. The data presented for GWMF (top row) corresponds directly to the samples shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 10 Same as Fig. 9 but for vertical wavelengths (top) and orientation of the GW (bottom). Sometimes the horizontal direction can 'flip', i.e., turn by $\pm\pi$, if the data in the cuboid is noisy. This leads to the negative sloped diagonal in the scatter plot.

1.3 Effect of data gaps on good data

We consider the effect that the gaps have on the surrounding 'good' data by investigating the RMSD (Root Means Square Deviation) of all data point pairs (REF and GAP) for the GW parameters obtained outside of the gaps versus the reference data without any gaps. Subsequently, a number of measurements adjacent to the measurement gaps were dismissed in order to assess the effect depths that the measurement gaps have on the retrieved GW parameters. The resulting RMSDs are shown in Fig. 11 for all four gap width simulations. Note that this RMSD is calculated from a sub-sample of observations and is, hence, not directly comparable to the values given in Fig 9 and 10.

It is apparent that the effect of 4 ALT samples wide gaps on the regions outside of the measurement gaps is rather small and that the effect of all simulations diminished to this base level at around 3 S3D sampling points distance to the gaps. Since the S3D sampling is about

150 km, the maximum extent of the deterioration due to the gaps, as seen from Fig. 11 is located about 450 km to either end of the gap. Therefore, the data loss is quite a bit higher than just the gaps of 9 ALT samples, at about 1050-1350 km in total (450 km gap \pm 300-450 km on either side). At that point, however, the data has not reached the quality of the 4 ALT samples gap. A gap of 7 ALT samples is much more forgiving with the data not as strongly degraded at the gap borders but still stronger degraded than the 4 point gap up to three sampling points away from the gap (resulting in a data-degradation gap compared to the 4 ALT samples gap of about 1250 km).

Figure 11 RMSD of vertical wavelength, horizontal wavelength, and orientation outside of the measurement gaps. The x-axis gives the distance to the gap where the cut of the analyzed data was set. Note that the S3D sampling in the along-track direction corresponds to 150 km, i.e., with each point in the plot, a single S3D sample is dropped to either end of every gap.

1.4 Conclusion

We investigated the effect of different sized streaks of consecutively missing spectra every 30th measurement on the instrument’s capability for resolving GWs. The small-volume S3D wave analysis tool is used for deriving GW parameters and GWMF.

As a general conclusion, the considered measurement gaps can be seen as another source of noise in the GW spectra which is mostly filtered out by cropping to wavelengths between 100 km and 3500 km in the horizontal and 2.8 km and 33 km in the vertical. The measurement gaps do not affect the ability to observe strong individual GW events with CAIRT and mainly lead to an increase in variability in regions with less GW activity.

Gaps of 4 ALT samples pose no severe hindrance for the GW analysis: The spectra are still very comparable to the reference without measurement gaps and the region of strong data degradation is limited mostly to the gap itself, i.e., a 200 km stretch of the orbit. With 6 or 7 missing spectra, the GW analysis starts to deteriorate beyond the gap, resulting in a data-loss of a stretch of about 900-1250 km along the orbit. However, the effect of 6 missing ALT samples on the resulting variables is still low enough to ensure the mission performance. Longer measurement gaps of 9 ALT samples deteriorate the data far beyond the measurement gap and should definitely be avoided.

2 Influence of dead sub-samples

This section investigates the effect of potentially dead pixel on the retrieval capabilities of GWs, in particular, the GWMF.

2.1 Setup & Experiment

We compare three different retrieval setups. One standard retrieval with all sub-samples intact (REF) and two retrievals where 2% (DS1) and 10% (DS2) of the sub-samples are defective. In particular, the specified fraction of sub-samples is ignored during the retrieval. The subsequent wave analysis is performed with the same parameters as in Sec. 1. Note, however, that the dataset represents a different date than in the previous section.

2.2 Results

Similar to the effect of calibration gaps in Sec. 1, we compare GW spectra, zonal-mean GWMF, phase-speed-direction spectra, and vertical wavelength and orientation directly.

2.2.1 GW spectra

The GW spectra for the three different simulations is shown in Fig. 12. Apparently, the spectra are very similar. The lack of information due to the defective sub-samples is not sufficient for a deterioration of the GW spectra.

Figure 12 Histogram of vertical wavelenghts (vertical axis) vs. horizontal wavelenghts (horizontal axis) weighted by the absolute GWMF. Shown are the results for no defective sub-samples (a), 2% dead sub-samples (b), and 10% dead sub-samples (c).

2.2.2 Zonal-mean GWMF

Figure 13 shows the zonal mean GWMF as determined from the different retrieval setups in 2° latitude bins. As for the GW spectra, the zonal-mean GWMF is very comparable and deviates only very slightly, which is mostly irrelevant. In addition, the variability of GWMF along a circle of constant latitude is almost identical between the simulations.

Figure 13 Zonal-mean absolute GWMF derived from the three different retrievals. In latitude, a 2° binning has been used. The shaded area shows the variability, i.e., the standard deviation, in a given latitude bin.

2.2.3 Phase-speed - direction spectra

The derived phase-speed-direction spectra are shown in Fig. 14. All three spectra are very similar with only minor fluctuations in the phase speeds. The average phase speeds are basically identical for the directions where significant GWMF exists. The only negative indications might be seen in Fig. 14c, where a overly strong component in south-east direction is seen. Therefore,

10% dead sub-samples might slightly add to the noise in the phase-speed-direction spectra. However, the effect of calibration gaps is much more severe, such that the small deviations here could be neglected.

Figure 14 GW phase-speed - direction spectra for the reference simulation (a), 2% dead sub-samples (b), and 10% dead sub-samples (c). Radial direction shows the propagation direction of the GWs, radial distance the phase speed, and the color shading the summed absolute GWMF in the respective bin.

2.2.4 Parameter comparison

Figure 15 gives insight in the effect of the dead sub-samples into the derived vertical wavelengths (top row) and orientation (bottom row). The scatter is very localized around identity for both simulation setups, indicating that the derived parameters are almost identically to the reference simulation without any dead sub-samples. The GW parameters can, hence, be derived with high confidence up to 10% dead sub-samples. An overview of the scatter widths of horizontal wavelength, vertical wavelength, and orientation is shown in Table 2.

Figure 15 Comparison of vertical wavelengths (top row) and orientations (bottom row) between the reference simulations (x -axes) and the simulations with dead sub-samples (y -axes). Left column shows the simulations with 2% dead pixel and right column shows the simulation with 10% dead sub-samples.

Table 2 RMSD of the scatter distribution of the respective variable vs. reference simulation. See also Fig. 15.

Variable	DS1	DS2
vert. wavelength	0.69 km	0.78 km
hor. wavelength	120 km	114 km
orientation	0.234	0.245

2.3 Conclusion

All in all, our analysis shows that the dead sub-samples don't affect the GW analysis strongly. Up to 10% dead sub-samples will most likely not deteriorate the GW products (GW spectra, phase-speed direction spectra, and GW parameters). Therefore, there is no technical requirement

other than the fraction of dead sub-samples should be no higher than 10% (as more have not been tested here).

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